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The new role of social work: the social worker-client relationship in the digitalised society as hotline-level bureaucracy

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the evolving role of social workers in the context of increasing digitalisation, focussing on the Czech Republic. Using ecological systems theory and the shift from street-level to screen-level bureaucracy as a framework, we analyse how digital tools are reshaping the relationship between clients and social workers, as well as professional boundaries. Using qualitative data from focus groups and interviews with social workers who support families at risk, we introduce the concept of 'hotline-level bureaucracy' to describe a recently emerged practice. In this model, social workers increasingly act as intermediaries between clients and digitalised institutions, often taking on responsibilities due to clients lacking access to technology and digital skills. This shift challenges the empowerment paradigm in social work, burdening practitioners with emotional and cognitive overload, and complicating ethical boundaries. We contend that this transformation necessitates a redefinition of roles, stronger institutional support, and broader structural responses to digital inequality.

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Introduction

Digitalisation of social work is a complex and multilayered process that can bring both advantages and disadvantages. In terms of advantages, first, digital communication can bring social work closer to certain target groups. This typically includes younger clients, who are used to communicating primarily online so establishing a rapport or relationship with them is easier, and hard-to-reach populations that are coping with spatio-temporal restrictions (Nordesjö et al., 2022; Randolph et al., 2023; Schmidt, 2024). Second, digital platforms have a potential to enhance the opportunity for clients to obtain relevant information, increase their involvement and participation, and, as a result, improve their empowerment (Breit et al., 2021; Saukkonen et al., 2024). Third, digital communication can be useful in some emotionally straining situations where clients do not want to communicate face-to-face. In these situations, better relationships can be established and strengthened (Schmidt, 2024). Fourth, it has been argued that digital systems produce

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and interconnect data in such a way that it enables social workers to make better informed decisions about allocation of resources, effectively improving social prevention (Saukkonen et al., 2024).

However, digitalisation and its advantages are sometimes regarded as a politically and morally neutral enhancement of ‘old’ and ‘ineffective’ face-to-face social work. Studies have shown that it is not necessarily the case, as digitalisation can produce new forms of structural vulnerabilities and moral ambiguities (Aasback, 2022; Pors & Schou, 2021). The most stressed disadvantage has been digital inequality, that is worsening of the access to social services for unprivileged and marginalised populations (e.g. poor families, homeless people, formerly incarcerated persons, drug users and the list goes on) who do not have the material means and proper skills to effectively utilise digital platforms (Hansen et al., 2018; Nordesjö et al., 2022; Pors & Schou, 2021; Ryan & Garrett, 2018; Sanders & Scanlon, 2021). Some authors (López-Peláez et al., 2025) argue that the problem extends beyond access itself and include digital vulnerability, which affects the wider population in increasingly digitised welfare systems. Second, digital instruments can also make it harder for social workers to establish proper relationships with clients, as the absence of face-to-face interactions limits the engagement of both the sides. In some cases, digital interactions can create a sense of distance (Nordesjö et al., 2022; Ryan & Garrett, 2018; Schmidt, 2024). Third, better and broader availability of social services also means boundary fluidity and blurriness for social workers who are seen as available all the time and may have difficulties in terms of maintaining professional relationships (Randolph et al., 2023; Ryan & Garrett, 2018). In the worst scenario, fluidity and blurriness with sometimes malfunctioning software and hardware can induce the feeling of technostress (Scaramuzzino & Martinell Barfoed, 2023). Fourth, data-driven social work can also have detrimental effects on clients who are under (constant) surveillance via the social media platforms (e.g. Facebook) in some cases, creating a tension between care and control (Nordesjö et al., 2022; Randolph et al., 2023). On an institutional level, there is the Netherlands case where the ‘digital welfare system’ responsible for evaluating social assistance has been implemented. It has been reported that based on stereotyping and stigmatising data, this system wrongly accused and punished thousands of people of child benefit fraud (Zajko, 2023).

In our study, we aim to explore more the client-social worker relationship within the framework of social services digitalisation and take a closer look at the Czech Republic case, which provides some new nuances that have not been analysed in other studies.

Theorising the client-social worker relationship

The relationship between the client and the social worker has long been at the centre of social work practice. It is not merely a technical or administrative interaction, but a dynamic and ethically loaded encounter shaped by human need, systemic constraints, and sociostructural conditions. Theorising this relationship is essential for understanding how it functions, evolves, and is challenged, particularly in the context of shifting paradigms such as digitalisation and bureaucratic restructuring.

An influential approach to conceptualising this relationship is the Life Model of social work practice, developed by Carel Germain and Alex Gitterman (Germain & Gitterman, 1996; Gitterman et al., 2021). Grounded in ecological and systems theories, the Life

Model views individuals in constant interaction with their environments. Problems do not reside solely within the individual, but emerge from a poor fit or stress between person and environment. The social worker's role then is to facilitate better person-environment interactions by empowering clients to navigate their environments and working to influence environmental forces to respond to people's needs.

In this model, the client – worker relationship is framed as a partnership, characterised by advocacy, collaboration, and shared commitment to change. Social workers support clients in becoming self-advocates rather than fostering dependency. Social workers act as facilitators of change, helping clients adapt to stress, improving the fit within their environments and modifying environmental barriers or stressors that negatively affect the clients. Professional boundaries remain crucial: flexible enough to support authentic engagement, yet clear enough to preserve ethical integrity, prevent burnout, and guard against over-involvement. As Germain, Gitterman and colleagues (Germain & Gitterman, 1996; Gitterman et al., 2021) note, reflexivity, role clarity, and the balance between empathy and professionalism are foundational. In the digital age, these principles face new challenges.

Digitalisation has profoundly reshaped the way client-social worker relationships are initiated, maintained, and experienced. According to Reamer (2015), new forms of boundary confusion arise in online environments. For example, clients can search for private information about workers or misinterpret refusals of social media requests as rejection. Meanwhile, social workers face ethical dilemmas regarding confidentiality, self-disclosure, and conflict in digital spaces. As Chechak (2015) points out, social workers can experience 'moral distress' when institutional limitations (such as funding or technology) prevent them from acting in line with their values.

These transformations align with theoretical shifts from street-level bureaucracy (Lipsky, 2010) to what scholars now describe as screen-level or system-level bureaucracy (Bovens & Zouridis, 2002). The classic concept of street-level bureaucracy (Lipsky, 2010) in which social workers (and any people working with other people) play a mediation role between formal rules set by authorities and clients to whom the rules should apply. In other words, through their interaction, discretion, and expertise skills, social workers are seen as front-line workers responsible for 'translating' social systems and policies to their users. Usually, street-level bureaucracy was done through establishing and maintaining face-to-face relationships with clients; however, recently, several studies pointed out that this has changed due to the digitalisation processes in societies.

Clients are increasingly motivated to employ electronic or digital systems for communication with public institutions, including welfare state ones, which results in change in the client-social worker relationship dynamics (Breit et al., 2021). In some cases, for example in Denmark, it means that the communication is digital by default and the ideal of self-serving citizens is implemented and maintained (Pors & Schou, 2021). In digital self-service, clients must acquire appropriate ICT skills enabling them to properly communicate with their institutions and social workers, as, for example, in Norway, where the digital activity plan, which is created by online collaboration between clients and social workers through dedicated digital application, is implemented (Aasback, 2022). Interactions with the system are often either automated or semiautomated, and social workers should interfere only in cases where clients are unable to fulfil their needs on their own and only to a necessary extent, meaning not to do anything for clients (Pors &

Schou, 2021; Saukkonen et al., 2024). These fundamental changes in the client-social worker interactions and relationships between clients and social workers led some scholars (Breit et al., 2021; Hansen et al., 2018) to re-examine the transformation from street-level bureaucracy to system-level bureaucracy or screen-level bureaucracy posed by Bovens and Zouridis (2002). Generally, within this transformation, street-level bureaucracy is weakened due to the digitalisation process, proliferation of remote communication, and reduction of face-to-face interactions. The street-level is then gradually replaced by screen-level and/or system-level, as the collaboration between the client and the social worker is influenced by the digital system and its creators, resulting in the necessity of conducting interactions in a specific way framed by the system, which then leaves less room for discretion of the social workers. Recently, Aasback (2022) termed social work influenced by these digitalisation trends as ‘platform social work’, pointing out some connections with platform and gig economies based on online, data-driven applications and services that play a mediation role between consumers and providers.

The transformation has similar (dis)advantages as the general ones mentioned above. Breit et al. (2021) recently analysed the digital coping of social workers who employed various strategies to address or alleviate the problems of digital interactions. In their research, the main issues were the availability of social workers for clients, the transparency of communication between clients and social workers, and the increased control of social workers’ text communication with clients. Social workers then, to cope with these issues, outsourced some digital responsibilities to clients (e.g. introduced digital platforms to clients who should then be able to help themselves), ‘reduced noise’, meaning cutting off unnecessary interactions (e.g. regarding proceduralism, or they filtered client requests), and formalised text communication with clients to prevent provision of an evidence for complaints, investigations or legal actions. In other studies, the possibility of miscommunication when using textual platforms was identified as an issue that has the potential to abruptly alter the relationship between the client and the social worker (Randolph et al., 2023; Schmidt, 2024). Some studies (Pors & Schou, 2021; Randolph et al., 2023; Ryan & Garrett, 2018; Saukkonen et al., 2024) also stressed that for transformation to work properly, the adequate ICT skills of both clients and social workers are required.

As the theory of the client – social worker relationship continues, it must now account for these technological and bureaucratic changes. Whether operating within the ecological paradigm or navigating the constraints of screen-level systems, social workers must remain attentive to the ethical, emotional, and practical implications of how they engage with clients. At its core, social work is still about human connection, advocacy, and transformation, but the tools, contexts, and boundaries through which that connection occurs are rapidly evolving.

Czech context

According to Datareportal (2025), in October 2025 the population of the Czech Republic reached 10.6 million inhabitants (75.0% of the population lives in urban regions, while 25.0% lives in rural areas). At the end of 2025, 9.96 million people used the internet in the Czech Republic, with an online penetration rate of 94.2%. The user figures indicate that 610 thousand people in the Czech Republic did not use the internet at the end of 2025,

which shows that 5.8% of the population remained ‘offline’ at the end of the year. In the Czech Republic, most social service users are members of communities that are most likely to be digitally excluded (Pisár et al., 2022). Clients who do not have access to the Internet, technology, or the necessary skills are left without support, or are dependent on mediated assistance through overloaded social services (Kalenda et al., 2023).

In the last decade, the Czech Republic has undergone a gradual digitalisation of public administration, which also significantly affects the field of social work. In the context of efforts to increase efficiency and reduce costs, digital systems are being implemented that change the way social work is performed (Jacob & Souissi, 2024). In the Czech Republic, the digitalisation of public administration, including social work, is taking place primarily in the form of the development of computerised systems for agendas such as benefit management, client records, or communication with citizens. The Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs has been investing significantly in digitalisation in recent years.

The benefit payment system is centralised under the Labour Office. A wide range of social benefits can only be applied for electronically. In some cases, assisted filing or personal visits are provided (depending on the specific situation). When submitting electronically via the Jenda client zone application, a data box, bank identity or citizen identity is required (GOV, 2025a). Similarly, the employment agenda no longer allows for the submission of unemployment benefits on a paper form, only online and either independently or assisted at a branch (GOV, 2025b). Although digitalisation is progressing, the network of branches is not equally available in all regions, which means that accessibility may be better in cities than in rural areas.

However, these changes are taking place in an environment where human and technological capital has long been undersized on the part of both civil servants and the nonstate non-profit sector, which leads to an overload of these organisations and at the same time threatens the availability and quality of services (Horák et al., 2021). The pressure for savings and efficiency then leads to the dismissal of civil servants and the transfer of the burden to other elements of the system, especially social services and their workers. They provide the missing advice and assistance to clients who cannot navigate the digital system. However, this comes up against insufficient capacities of social services in the area of digital skills, technical equipment, and staffing.

Czech social workers are, in some cases, stuck in a liminal position of not being the street-level bureaucrats anymore but also not being the screen-level bureaucrats yet. Clients are supposed to use digital platforms to apply, for instance, for social assistance, but do not have capacities, ICT skills, or actual hardware equipment to do so (Kalenda et al., 2023). On the other hand, social workers are supposed to support and empower clients to employ digital means and try to address their issues as they see fit, but they cannot do so because of the reasons stated above (Nordesjö et al., 2022). Therefore, as we shall see, Czech social workers cannot assist clients ‘on demand’, but they perpetually do the necessary processes with and for clients, effectively becoming hotline-level bureaucrats.

Methodology

The findings presented here are drawn from a subset of data created as part of a project “Excellent research in the field of digital technologies and well-being.” In this larger

study, our research sub-team focused on the digitalisation of social work with families with at-risk children. Through six focus groups and two individual interviews with social workers ($n = 36$), we sought to determine how social workers working with at-risk children understand the impact of digitalisation of society on the performance of their work.

Data were collected from September to November 2024 in selected social services focused on working with families with children and youth in four regions (out of a total of 14) in the Czech Republic. The regions were selected to capture diverse settlement and demographic patterns, including varying degrees of urbanisation, population density, and socio-demographic conditions, and ranging from highly urban to mixed and more rural-leaning regions.

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Social Studies, University of Ostrava, under the number of 42/2024.

Participants

Participants were purposefully selected through social service organisations with the aim to maximise variability of the selection (Patton, 1990), based on at least one year of experience with families with children at risk in a given type of service. Specifically, these were social activation services for families with children, low-threshold facilities for children and youth, outreach programmes for children and youth, or accompanying foster families. These were non-profit organisations that are an integral part of the social service system. They often provide innovative, community-oriented and flexibly responsive services, complementing the public sector. At same time, social work carried out by NGOs has been responsible for mediating contact between clients and public institutions and/or other organisations. For example, this includes assisting clients throughout the process of application for social assistance provided by Labour Offices; or assisting when clients apply for ID cards or other documents at various public offices.

In total, six focus groups were conducted with the number of participants ranging from 3 to 8. An individual interview was conducted with two participants due to their time constraints. There were 30 women and 6 men with a length of practice that was most often between 6 and 15 years and most often between the ages of 41–50.

Data creation

Social workers were contacted through their workplace. We contacted the organisations via an introductory letter sent by email. This described the research project, the purpose of the research, information on data management, and contacts for researchers. If they agreed, a meeting was arranged according to their preferences, most often directly at the organisation.

The research team developed the focus group and the interview guide. At the beginning, the participants were informed about the purpose of the discussion and its rules and informed consent was obtained. First, a general question was asked about the impact of digitalisation on social work, the participants created a flip chart list of areas through the moderators, which they then grouped into themes and subthemes. They then selected 3 themes to discuss.

A participant card was filled out with each participant. The interviews lasted one to two hours and were conducted by a total of six researchers. The focus groups were conducted in pairs, and individual interviews were always conducted by one researcher. Focus groups and interviews were transcribed verbatim, anonymised, and stored on a secure server. The research team inductively coded each transcript in MAXQDA 22 software, resulting in the development of an initial coding framework, which was then analysed via reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022). During the analysis, several themes were created out of the codes with an emphasis on the principles of reflexive thematic analysis: themes do not emerge from the data, but are creatively construed by analysts; themes contain some stories that can be told; themes should be specific and have a particular and punching name; and themes should be interconnected with literature during presentation, not afterwards in the discussion section. In the next section, due to the space constraints, we present one of the themes: hotline-level bureaucracy. This theme was, in some form, emphasised throughout the data by participants, and represented well the Czech way of social assistance system digitalisation.

Findings – hotline-level bureaucracy theme¹

The theme is based on the participants' perspective that digitalisation of social work has been bringing often completely new dynamics to the social worker-client relationships and, generally, a change of the social workers' role in the process of supporting their clients. Since the principle digital by default has been progressing as the standard for communication (Pors & Schou, 2021), informants felt that their clients do not have economic means and capacities to keep going with it for various reasons. The first was the digital gap and marginalised position of clients who simply did not have the actual instruments (computers, mobile phones, tablets, etc.) and/or platforms (emails, on-line call accounts, etc.) to begin and maintain the communication:

[...] if clients want to go to a job, they are supposed to send CVs, but when they don't have mobile phones, they cannot start an e-mail address and send it because the mail relates to a phone number. At this moment, they are limited because they cannot communicate. (Hodavka, focus group, region 1)

[...] there are online meetings with applicants for admission to therapeutic communities. (Hajma, focus group, region 1)

According to Hodavka and Hajma, clients without the proper electronic means do not have a chance to start, for example, in a job or apply for treatment in a therapeutic community. Social workers then have difficulty fulfilling client contracts unless they bridge this gap and are prepared to provide the means necessary for this bridging, which could be considered as a violation of the rules of organisation:

Sometimes, we sit him [a client] on a computer so that he can check his email and reply. (Ledan, interview, region 2)

However, for Ledan, this was only a temporary solution, as she felt that the provision of means invites clients to transfer their responsibilities to social workers as well as providing them with personal data (e.g. passwords):

[...] many of our clients are willing to give us their access credentials to e-mails and task us to check the account for new mails, ideally reply to them, or give them an echo that some work agency got in touch or something. (Ledan, interview, region 2)

Therefore, according to Ledan, some clients take advantage, and social workers must strictly establish boundaries and stress the temporality of the situation so that clients do not end up disempowered. Ledan called this situation 'mutual pushing over the competencies'.

Other informants also mentioned the client's dependency on the provided electronic means and the transfer of responsibilities in various other situations.

It often happens that clients seeking housing or a job give my work number and e-mail address. I get several calls from different people, and I don't even know who it is. [...] Because they [clients] have my card where they have my phone number and email [...] (Bojata, focus group, region 1)

Paying with a bank account is also a problem. [...] recently, one client wanted to pay for the school group in cash, but they told her in the school that it was not possible since they didn't accept cash. So, she had to send it via bank account, but she didn't have one. So who would mediate it? So we had been thinking that it could be us. [the NGO] (Oskora, focus group, region 1)

[...] I have experience with the energy payment transfer when, at the beginning, I assisted my client, she gave her ID there, I gave my ID [...] and then everything went through my work e-mail. Everything was communicated via email, the contract, transfer [...] I'm the middleman. When I receive anything from my email, I print it, visit the client, hand over the document, or I open the document on my phone and the client would sign it. (Milica, focus group, region 2)

All informants described how they got the position of the intermediary when assisting their clients with different issues. In the Bojata case, she was set up to that position by her clients, who automatically provided her personal credentials when needed. Oskora presented the case of one client where the NGO resolved the possibility that the client's children would not have the school group to attend. And in the case of Milica, the energy company imposed the middleman role on her because she was more credible in the eyes of the company than the client herself. Typically, social workers would also help clients with document scanning, storing electronic document, e-communication with institutions, filling up on-line applications, etc.

Therefore, whenever it was necessary to resolve some communication or practical problems that clients did not have the means to address, social workers would step up and settle the situation. On top of it, social workers not only resolved the actual situation but also kept in touch with organisations in case of further complications. The role of informants not only blurs the professional boundaries (Randolph et al., 2023; Ryan & Garrett, 2018) but also resembles the hotline support, the continual and almost constantly present guidance that can solve the client issues for them. Therefore, informants became hotline-level bureaucrats; they translated social policy as well as the digital by default approach to clients, constantly at their disposal due to the digitalisation of communication and the dependency on provision of technological means.

Not surprisingly, the hotline-level bureaucracy position was seen by informants as very demanding:

It is a completely different form of collaboration because, suddenly, you have the responsibility to mediate the information. (Senata, focus group, region 2)

It forces us to take over the clients' responsibilities, instead of empowering them. She [a client] would receive an email, contact us if she don't know what to do, and I should help her. OK, but, this way, I'm the one taking the obligation. (Milica, focus group, region 2)

[...] transfer of responsibility in the digitalisation context [...] is mostly burdensome. I don't mind dealing with client mail, but if I must pass on when something beeps [text message in mobile phone] I feel tied up that I have agreed to it. That's the burden. (Chrza, focus group, region 2)

As all of the excerpts point out, informants were overloaded with the responsibility to check the electronic communication for clients and mediate the important messages as well as being constantly on guard not to miss the messages. However, as Chrza later in the interview mentioned, there was no other opportunity for social workers to maintain collaboration with clients and address their needs, as, again, clients did not have the appropriate means to do it themselves. In this sense, some informants feared that they fail to mediate an important piece of information, which would result in problems for clients. Thus, they experienced technostress, but not due to malfunctioning software or hardware (Scaramuzzino & Martinell Barfoed, 2023), but paradoxically because well-functioning electronic communication increased the burden.

Technostress was also supported by the digital by default approach that brought a broader spectrum of clients, who had not needed any support before, into a collaboration with social services:

We fear that it [digitalisation] will overwhelm social services [...] that even people who did not need support would require it. So the number of people who need assistance will increase, but, at the same time, the rest of things [social work interventions] would also stay the same. (Hajma, focus group, region 1)

Hajma's fears were confirmed by Schou and Pors (2019) in their study, in which they pointed out that digitalisation of social services meant more people seeking help due to the unfamiliarity with new electronic systems and processes. For some informants, this increasing burden and overloading in combination with the hot-line level bureaucracy required a harm reduction or damage management approach:

Transitions to a better efficiency [e.g. digitalisation] always fall on the marginalised [...] and I think it's our job in social services to smooth the edge so that as few people as possible are hurt. (Mirogoj, focus group, region 1)

Mirogoj then expressed a divisiveness during the focus group where, on the one hand, he admitted that he uses technologies a lot and was not pessimistic towards them, but, on the other hand, felt that technologies can often have a devastating impact on clients. He then also articulated a little bit of a resignation over the situation, as, according to him, the technological advancement cannot be stopped, so, in the context of social workers

overburdening, the only option is trying to mitigate its negative effects falling on the marginalised populations.

This was also experienced by other informants who voiced an effort to educate clients about the digital world and its risks. This education was often carried out without the client's request and happened more randomly than systematically.

It's [digital education] not something regular because other issues are more pressing. Clients want to address the issues that are endangering their life, housing, and finances. It doesn't occur to them that they have poor digital literacy. (Chrza, focus group, region 2)

Clients did not perceive that they have any problems with digital technologies or that they can be victimised by technologies, so, often, informants had to bring up the issue on their own, sometimes using rather control strategy than supportive one:

[...] when I have him [a client] in [Facebook] friends, I can see that [some inappropriate online behaviour] and write to hide ID numbers [...] I appreciate the children, but at the same time I tell them that they are not supposed to do this. I trained one of my clients in the way that when she is posting something, she hides everything. (Milica, focus group, region 2)

[...] through control of parents, we can educate them about some digital competencies [...] [so that] they can set boundaries for their children in terms of using the technologies. (Mrava, focus group, region 4)

[...] [we educate them] that some scammer can call them so that they should be able to say no or drop the call. Or there are these bitcoins, right? I believe that they received text messages with this so some of them could be misled to invest. (Beneda, focus group, region 4)

Education took various forms: behaviour on social media, parenting in terms of setting boundaries of using technologies, or protection from scammers and their victimisation. Other informants also added education about using email or how to recognise disinformation and not share it. It is worth noting that, in the cases of Milica and Mrava, education took more paternalistic outlines, as they tended to control their clients and direct their behaviour in a 'proper' way. In addition, Milica did this through her private social media account, which also blurred the boundaries between social workers and clients. Ledan then clearly expressed that he is aware of his controlling style of collaboration with clients:

[...] sometimes we watch over the parents. When we have them in meetings, we ask them whether they have checked out their email. Schools are sending mails with a lot of information. Often, they say that they haven't so we would then check the email in my office and find several mails. We then try to reply. [...] (Ledan, focus group, region 2)

However, it was not Ledan's, and some other participants, desire to control clients' behaviour or punish non-compliance, but rather as an effort to maintain control over the situation. This included, for instance, ensuring digital communication with the school and shield families from the potential risks and sanctions that might arise if institutional expectations are not met, which could otherwise lead to greater difficulties for the family and increased workload for the social worker.

This tendency to control was, again, connected to over-burdening of informants who expressed that education of clients is very demanding, especially in the context of doing the rest of the agenda. Hajma and Chrza captured it illustratively:

Working with information at this time when everyone is overflowed with it is something that we were unable to solve. We have brought it up how to speak with clients about it [...] How do we address this? Probably with some interviewing but it's, again, very limiting to significantly influence people or educate them on how to critically read the news. That's a skill that cannot be learnt throughout one intervention. (Hajma, focus group, region 1)

[...] it's [digital education] very demanding in terms of time. When I see the family once a week, I need to address something pressing. It's not real for me to involve digital security into the interaction. (Chrza, focus group, region 2)

Some informants also did not see themselves as proper experts in digital technologies education since they themselves knew only the basics, so they were unsure whether they had the qualification to educate clients.

Conclusive discussion

In the theme we presented, informants voiced the story of having hardships with maintaining the client relationship in the sense of the Life Model concept (Germain & Gitterman, 1996; Gitterman et al., 2021) due to the digitalisation of social work. Facilitation of social workers' activities between clients and their environment has proven to be very difficult and demanding in the advancing digitalisation context. In this sense, clients lacked economic means (i.e. actual hardware), capacities, and competencies, and were unable to meet the social expectations of everyone's digital proficiency on which the digital by default approach is based (Pors & Schou, 2021). The digital by default approach is, according to our informants, manifesting itself in the transformation of interaction with public institutions that began to require communication through digital platforms. This all has fundamentally changed the social work role of the informants in the way that they had to provide the actual technological instruments (computers, mobile phones, etc.) to their clients to even start/maintain the communication with public institutions. At the same time, informants began to educate their clients about digital technologies and how to use them. On the other hand, clients began to be dependent on the provision of technological instruments and tended to transfer some of their obligations onto informants, for example, checking emails, answering to phone calls, mediating the text messages, and general communication, etc. This situation is, interpreted from the Life Model standpoint, problematic as it weakens the empowerment of clients, both from the individual and structural perspectives since the empowerment environment is not created and clients are not properly engaged in the social work process. At the same time, it needs to be emphasised that this disempowerment is not a desire of social workers, but rather a product of structural vulnerability of families that keeps pushing social workers to do harm reduction. In this regard, it is worth exploring more in future research whether the harm reduction strategy is alleviating the vulnerability problem or deepening it.

However, the lack of empowerment and involvement of clients is not the only main outcome. When we look at the situation through the lenses of the traditional street-level bureaucracy concept (Lipsky, 2010) and newer versions, such as

screen-level or system-level bureaucracy (Bovens & Zouridis, 2002; Breit et al., 2021; Hansen et al., 2018), we can see that the role of social workers is fundamentally changing. Our informants were not simple translators between clients and (digitalised) public institutions with a certain level of discretion at their disposal. They were always ready to assist with education, communication mediation and arrangements for clients, effectively becoming hotline-level bureaucrats, ready to address any problem on demand. Many informants saw this transformation as overburdening, disempowering, and generally stressful, but at the same time, necessary to help their clients and keep them in social services. Without the hotline-level bureaucracy, many clients would not simply have entered the services or maintained collaboration, as they did not have the necessary means. However, due to their limited capacities, informants also felt that the agenda concerning digitalisation should not be in their management, since they have the usual full-time social work agenda. Because of this, some of them expressed some resignation about the situation and perceived their role of the hotline-level bureaucrats in terms of harm reduction or damage management. From this standpoint, the position of hotline-level bureaucrat can be perceived as liminal. Our informants clearly ceased to be street-level bureaucrats but, at same time, have not yet become screen-level bureaucrats who would just help clients with their digital self-service as it is done elsewhere (Aasback, 2022; Breit et al., 2021; Pors & Schou, 2021; Saukkonen et al., 2024). The insecurity of this liminal position was also reproduced by technostress (Scaramuzzino & Martinell Barfoed, 2023) experienced by some informants who felt overwhelmed by digital technologies and demands of their clients, or accidentally not fulfilling them, respectively.

The lesson for social work practice is quite straightforward: the liminal position of a hotline-level bureaucrat is a product of social work neoliberalisation, where social workers address individually the structural problems, mainly marginalisation of clients who are singled out from the digitalisation process. However, an informant, Hajma, offered a practical intervention for alleviating the problem that every organisation should have at least one digitally specialised social worker who would be proficient in digitalisation and would focus on the digital agenda exclusively.

As for the limits of our study, the data were created in four Czech regions, so it is possible that social workers in other regions would have different experiences and bring up other incentives. This applies also to the type of the social service we have done the research with, where we focused on social services working with families and at-risk children, and, again, other types of social services may have some differences in the social worker-client relationship.

Note

1. Informant were given old Czech names for ethical and anonymisation reasons.

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Ethics statement

The Ethics Committee for Research at the Faculty of Social Studies, University of Ostrava, approved this research project on 8 August 2024.

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